

HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

PERSEUS

2D Material-Based Multiple Oncotherapy Against Metastatic Disease Using a Radically New Computed Tomography Approach

DELIVERABLE

WP1 – D1.2 – Data Management Plan (DMP)

ABSTRACT

This document provides details on all the research data collected and generated within the PERSEUS project. It explains the way research data are handled, organized, licensed and made available to the public, and how they will be preserved after the project is completed.

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Deliverable Name	Data Management Plan
Deliverable Number	1.2
Lead beneficiary	BeD
Deliverable Type	DMP
Work package title	Project Management
Work package number	WP1
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Due Date	31-08-2023

Revision history				
Version	Date	Authors	Partner	Remarks
1.1	10/07/2023	Evie L. Papadopoulou	BeD	First draft
1.1.1	23/07/2023	Jeny Shklover	Technion	Revision and contribution to sections 1 and 3
1.1.2	25/07/2023	L.M.C. Giberti	QED	Revision and contribution to sections 2 and 6
1.2	02/08/2023	Evie L. Papadopoulou	BeD	Integration of contributions from Technion and QED
1.2.1	04/08/2023	Nicoletta Marigo	CNR	General revision for consistency and coherence
1.2.2	07/08/2023	Giancarlo Salviati	CNR	Contribution to sections 2, 3, 4 and 6
1.2.3	15/08/2023	Bengt Fadeel	KI	Contribution to sections 1 and 2
1.2.4	27/08/2023	Giancarlo Salviati	CNR	Final revision
1.3	28/08/2023	Evie L. Papadopoulou	BeD	Consolidation and finalization

Approved by: Nicoletta Marigo (CNR)

Date of approval: 9 August 2023

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This document is in accordance with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement which requires that a data management plan (DMP) is established and regularly updated. The document follows the template recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries and addresses the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17.

This DMP reflects the current state of the art of the PERSEUS project which is in month 6 (M6) at the time of writing. However, the details on the types, format, size and origin of the data sets may vary during the research project. The variations will be recorded in updated versions of this DMP.

1. Data Summary

1.1. Reuse of any existing data

PERSEUS is an innovative project that will build new hybrid material-systems that will fulfil the requirements for low energy X-ray absorption. Stringent material requirements must be followed, for instance in terms of size, morphology, X-ray absorption, reactive oxygen species (ROS) production etc. As a result, no such materials, or data, are currently available that might result in the desirable outcome. Therefore, no re-use of existing data is foreseen for the moment (M6).

The cell culture and animal experiments will be conducted following literature and protocols that have been previously developed by the project partners. However, all the experimental data will be exclusively generated using PERSEUS innovative hybrid material-systems, and there are no plans for data re-use at this time (M6).

1.2. Purpose and Technical details

The purpose of the generated data during PERSEUS is to develop a new therapeutic approach for the treatment of deep-seated, clinically unmanageable, drug-resistant, and metastatic tumours. This approach is based on the development of multifunctional, hybrid nano-vehicles, namely 2D transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) functionalised with metal nanoparticles (NPs) and organic photosensitisers (PSs) encapsulated in liposomes. These nano-vehicles will be activated by low energy X-rays that will be delivered by modified CT clinical scanners and/or low energy X-ray devices.

The designed experiments will range from materials fabrication and characterisation to *in vitro* and *in vivo* assessment of tumour eradication under low X-ray radiation, resulting in a wide variety of data.

Data generated in the lifetime of the project will be first evaluated for (i) dissemination or (ii) exploitation. In the first case it will be published, presented, or disseminated in any appropriate way, whereas in the latter case, it will be protected via the IPR, and it will be disseminated after any possible applied embargo period will have passed.

In the following Tables (1 to 5) we show the correlation of the data generated in the lifetime of PERSEUS with the different objectives of the project as these are expressed via the different WPs and Tasks, as described in the Grant Agreement. Some technical details are also presented, however they are indicative since we are at the start of the project (M6). Subsequent versions of the DMP might be updated as appropriate.

Table 1

Objective: Engineering NS with the desired X-ray induced physical properties (WP2)

Task	Lead Beneficiary	Data Generated	Origin of data	Format	Size
2.1 Liquid-phase exfoliation and characterisation of 2D nanocrystals.	BeD	Experimental data on exfoliation parameters and characterisation of produced 2D materials	TEM, AFM, Raman, UV-vis absorption, XRD, XPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .doc • .txt • .tiff • .jpeg 	1G
2.2 Metal NP fabrication, characterisation, & grafting on the 2D-NCs	UVIGO	Experimental data on (i) gold NP grafting (size, coverage) on 2D-NCs and (ii) NP green synthesis by natural extracts.	TEM (HREM, STEM, EDX) Raman, AFM, TGA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .doc • .tiff • .jpeg • .ppt 	n.a.
2.3 Functionalisation of metal NPs / 2D nanocrystals with PS	CNR	Experimental data on (i) metal NPs (gold, silver and platinum) synthesis with photosensitizers and (ii) functionalisation of the abovementioned NPs or 2D nanocrystals with photosensitisers.	UV-Vis , FTIR Fluorescence, Z-potential, DLS TEM (HREM, STEM, EDX) XRD, TGA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .doc • .txt • .tiff • .jpeg • .ppt 	n.a.

2.4 Design refinement for max ROS production efficiency	CNR	Experimental data on ROS and in particular singlet oxygen generation by using selective probes	Fluorescence; UV-vis spectroscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .doc • .txt • .tiff • .jpeg • .ppt 	n.a.
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Table 2**Objective: Developing CT specifications to trigger the NSs (WP2)**

Task	Lead Beneficiary	Data Generated	Origin of data	Format	Size
2.5 Theory & modelling of NS X-ray absorption, heating, & electron emission yield	WIGNER	Calculated data	Theoretical simulation programs	pdf	1-20 MB
2.6 Characterisation of NS X-ray absorption, heating, and electron emission yield; refinement of the design	WIGNER	Experimental data	Spectrometers and other detectors	ASCII file (TXT, RAW, DAT)	1-20 MB

Table 3**Objective: In-vitro validation of NV design and functionality (WP3)**

Task	Lead Beneficiary	Data Generated	Origin of data	Format	Size
3.1 Formulation, encapsulation, characterisation of liposomes with the NSs	IIT	Experimental data about cellular uptake and absorption (Size, structure and stability characterization)	Raman spectroscopy and mapping DLS Z-potential Microscopy Cryo-Tem	ASCII file (TXT, DAT) .xlsx .zmes .png .jpeg .tiff	1-20 MB

3.2 Characterisation of the nanovehicle biocorona in relevant biological media	KI	Experimental data on the protein composition of the corona.	Mass spectrometry data (proteomics)	mzML format is an open, XML-based format for mass spectrometer output files.	MB-GB
3.3 Targeting molecule selection and conjugation to the nanovehicles	IIT	Experimental data on conjugation efficiency and in vitro analysis in cancer cells	TLC NMR Plate-reader ICP Microscopy	.jpeg .tiff .pdf .zip .xlsx	1-20 MB
3.4 Biocompatibility and biodegradability assessment of the nanovehicles	KI	Experimental data on toxicity/cytokine profiles and degradability using in vitro (cell-based) assays.	Single-cell mass cytometry Multi-plex cytokine array Raman confocal microscopy Cell viability assays (LDH)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FCS (for CyToF) • MSD (Mesoscale Discovery) • TIFF Excel 	1-20 MB
3.5 Assessment of nanovehicle effectiveness using 2D & 3D tumour models	KI	Experimental data from confocal microscope	Confocal microscopy	TIFF images	5-20 MB

Table 4**Objective: Pre-clinical proof-of-concept of NVs for cancer therapy in animal models (WP4)**

Task	Lead Beneficiary	Data Generated	Origin of data	Format	Size
4.1 Biodistribution and impact of targeting of the NVs	KI	Experimental data of organs targeting and biodistribution	Microscopy FACS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • png • .txt • .csv • .xlsx 	5-100 MB

			IVIS; ICP; Immunohistochemistry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .jpg • .tiff 	
4.2 In-vivo NV biocompatibility & biodegradability assessment	KI	Experimental data of metabolism	Metabolite detection, blood drug concentration test Microscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .xlsx • .txt • .jpg • .csv 	50-100 MB
4.3 In-vivo assessment of NV administration+irradiation in triple negative breast cancer	IIT	Experimental data of tumor growth	Tumor size, IVIS; Immunohistochemistry; Histological staining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .png • .txt • .csv • .xlsx • .jpg • .tiff 	5-30 MB
4.4 In-vivo assessment of nanovehicles+irradiation in deep-seated visceral cancers	KI	Experimental data of tumor growth and tumor microenvironment	Organ pictures; Growth curve; PET-CT IHC pictures; HE staining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .xlsx • .tiff • .jpg 	200-300 MB
4.5 Profiling tumor microenvironment with respect to immunocompetent cells	IIT	Experimental data of microenvironment and particles infiltration	IVIS; FACS; Immunohistochemistry; Proteomics; Microscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .png • .txt • .csv • .jpg • .tiff • .mzML 	5-30 MB

Table 5**Objective: Pre-clinical treatment of metastasis (WP4)**

Task	Lead Beneficiary	Data Generated	Origin of data	Format	Size
4.6 Direct (NV+X-rays) vs. immune-mediated effects on metastatic disease	KI	Experimental data of metastatic of X-rays and immune-mediated treatment	Organ pictures; Growth curve; IHC pictures; HE staining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .xlsx • .tiff • .jpg 	200-300 MB

1.3. Utility of generated data

The data generated within PERSEUS first and foremost will be useful to the Consortium and to the Advisory Board (after the signature of an NDA). However, the published generated data might be of use to stakeholders outside the project, including:

- Materials scientists
- Solid state physicists
- Chemists
- Biologists
- Medical doctors (e.g., oncologists)
- Pharmacists (e.g., working in the pharmaceutical sector)
- Universities (for instance Master's students)
- Regulatory Agencies
- Cancer patient advocacy groups

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data records will be uploaded to Zenodo, an open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. Zenodo offers the possibility to upload different kind of data records, such as research papers, datasets, research software, reports etc. Every upload in Zenodo is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), in order to make them findable and citable. DOI provided by Zenodo can be versioned, enabling the users to update the reports. Published papers can be uploaded using the DOI assigned to them by the journal.

Rich metadata will be provided for every PERSEUS record uploaded to Zenodo. Metadata will be documented in a text file (.txt), using the same identifier as the record. A different suffix/extension will be used to distinguish between record (e.g., dataset) and metadata.

Metadata for each dataset will include:

- Title
- Description

- Creator and contributors
- Specification of the data identifier(s)
- Publisher (if relevant)
- Date of data collection
- Dates of document creation and last revision
- Acknowledgement of the EC funding of the PERSEUS project

The naming of the uploaded datasets will be as following:

PERSEUS_DS_title_partner_dissemination_vsYYY

The different parts constituting the name, stand for the following:

- PESEUS: the name of the project
- DS: for datasets
- title: the title of the DS. It might also indicate the work package (WP), deliverable (DEL) etc.
- partner: the acronym of the partner (CNR, KI, IIT, UVIGO, BeD) that has generated the DS
- dissemination: indicating the level of dissemination (e.g. co = confidential, pu = public)
- vsYYY: the version of the dataset

For all reports uploaded to Zenodo, including metadata, search keywords will be assigned, in order to maximise the possibility for discovery.

2.2. Making data accessible

Data records will be uploaded to Zenodo, an online repository open to all researchers regardless of funding stream, geographical location or scientific field. Zenodo guarantees a free upload and access, this making scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for long term. With particular reference to proteomics data to be generated by PERSEUS (cf. protein corona task 3.2), the upload on database like ProteomeXchange will also be considered.

Data will have different accessibility levels, depending on the exploitation vs dissemination parameter:

- Data shared only within WPs
- Data shared with consortium (includes not yet published papers)
- Public (the scientific community, regulators, companies etc.)

An embargo period might be required before the publication of some research output, in order to ensure protection of the intellectual property. In general, embargo periods are case-dependent and will be used give time to publish and to seek protection for the intellectual properties. EU project deliverables that are public (PU) will be available as soon as possible. In case an embargo period is necessary, this will be clearly stated and the rationale behind this decision will be defined in the metadata file.

The exact duration will depend on the journal chosen and on the utility patent wait time for a first review and filing. At the time of writing it is too early to specify how long this will take and how long the embargo period will be. More information will be provided in subsequent versions of this document

Embargo period and closed access are provided by Zenodo. However, we may choose to not deposit exploitable results as their publication could compromise their protection and hence jeopardise their commercialisation prospects.

Considering the multidisciplinary nature of the project, data access should be requested to the project coordinator who, in turn, will contact the interested WP leaders for information and permission. In case of disagreement, the Executive Board of the project will be summoned to discuss the matter and decide on the access request.

According to the GA, metadata of publications, as well as of deposited data, will be openly available under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication CC0 license (latest version up to date is CC0-1.0). Metadata will clearly specify a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI) for each set of data, in addition to descriptive information about the data that, according to the GA, will include:

- Publication (author(s), title, date of publication, affiliation)
- Horizon Europe funding
- grant project name, acronym and number
- licensing terms
- persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Maybe not all data will be uploaded to Zenodo (see point 2.2). The PERSEUS consortium will make the accessible records as interoperable as possible, ensuing the following steps:

Generated data will be collected and documented in a standardised way in order to ensure that is correctly understood and hence re-used. To this end, standard ontologies will be used to describe all records uploaded to Zenodo (e.g., datasets, reports etc.). Vocabularies for keywords and other metadata properties have yet to be selected.

In the case where standard vocabulary cannot be used, a glossary will be included (and published alongside the datasets) describing the newly introduced ontologies.

If necessary, the data will include qualified references to other data, especially data from the project. It is still too early to say (M6), but probably we will have to use qualified references, due to the multidisciplinary nature of the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use

All data/records uploaded to Zenodo will be licenced according to their accessibility levels (defined in #2.2). According to the GA, the license used will be the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights. At the moment of writing, the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY), is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY-4.0). CC-BY-4.0 license allows third parties to share and adapt data with no restrictions as long as attribution is provided [<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>]. This license will be used for records (e.g. datasets etc). Metadata of the deposited data will be open under Creative Commons CCZero (CC0-1.0) (see also #2.2).

In the case where data needs to have more restricted accessibility, the type of licensing -and possible associated costs- will be decided further during the project, in conjunction with the Project Officer.

The usability of the data generated during the project by third parties shall be defined by the license applied to each set of data, that will, in turn, be defined by the accessibility level (see #2.2). Furthermore, for data of restricted accessibility, the licensing will be determined by the Exploitation report (D6.2 Exploitation Plan).

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards.

The quality of the data generated -and described in the metadata files- is the responsibility of the PERSEUS partner who is involved in the generation of the relevant data.

3. Other research outputs

Other research outputs that may be generated during PERSEUS include:

- New materials
- New experimental methods of X-radiation
- Simulation models
- Protocols for *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests

The management of any other possible research output will be covered in subsequent releases of the DMP.

4. Allocation of resources

At this initial stage of the project the costs relative to the curation of the data according to the FAIR principles are the person months (direct personnel costs) foreseen for each partner in the GA. Costs associated with making data FAIR include:

- Data archiving in the Zenodo platform: free of charge
- Copyright licensing with Creative Commons: free of charge
- Gold open access publishing: according to the GA, costs associated with Gold OA are eligible (Table 3.2h). In case of multiple partner institutions in the author list, the cost sharing will be decided among the authors and will be case dependent.
- Costs associated with hybrid journals are not eligible.

Later in the project, additional necessary costs might be identified, and properly justified.

Bedimensional S.p.a. is responsible for the development and the regular updating of the DMP and for providing enough guidance to the PERSEUS partners to comply with it. Responsibility for managing the

data generated throughout the project falls on all partners, as allocated in the different WPs and Tasks/Deliverables. All partners are requested to comply with the guidelines of the present DMP and the OpenAIRE procedures.

Data will be stored at least for 5 years after the end of the project.

Data storage in Zenodo is possible for up to at least 20 years.

5. Data security

Each consortium partner guarantees for the backup storage of their data. In addition, records uploaded to Zenodo will be stored in the CERN Data Centres in Geneva and Budapest. Multiple replicas are created in a distributed file system, further backed up on tape [<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>].

6. Ethics

PERSEUS is an interdisciplinary project, that involves the production of nanomaterials and their use in biomedical applications. Up to now (M6) we have not identified any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing, as is described in #2.2 of the present document. Furthermore, the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are outlined in the Consortium Agreement (Article 16) and will be further described under Task 6.2 and corresponding deliverable D6.1. IPR is in line with the general EC policies regarding ownership, exploitation rights, confidentiality, commercial utilization of results, availability of the information, and deliverables.

Nevertheless, if necessary, an ethics committee will be established, with one representative for each scientific partner, for the management of any ethics-related aspect of the data.